

Role of macro and micro elements on bioleaching of silica from Indian chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀

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Abstract : Bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ is performed to increase the chromium concentration in low grade chromite ore. The present study discuss about the role of nutritional factors necessary for the growth as well as bioleaching of silica from chromite. Besides carbon and nitrogen sources, the organism require macro elements like KH₂PO₄, KCl, MgSO₄·7H₂O, NaH₂PO₄ for their proper growth and silica bioleaching. Withdrawal of these elements from the fermentation media shows a significant decrease in both growth and bioleaching process. Elements like NaCl, CaCl₂ were found to have no significant effect on growth of the organism and bioleaching process. Among the micro elements, Fe²⁺ and Mn²⁺ showed a significant increase in the bioleaching of silica from chromite ore. Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺ (below 10 µg/ml) concentration and Cu²⁺ (below 5 µg/ml) were found to have no significant effect, but with increase in concentration, all three elements were found to inhibit growth and bioleaching. Co²⁺, Mo⁶⁺, V³⁺ were found to have no significant role in this process. After optimization of the fermentation media (glucose – 10%, NaNO₃ – 0.2%, KH₂PO₄ – 0.1%, KCl – 0.05%, MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.06%, NaH₂PO₄ – 0.05%, FeSO₄·7H₂O – 15 µg/ml, MnSO₄·H₂O – 10 µg/ml), 73.76% silica was found to be leached out from the ore.

Keywords : Silica, chromite ore, *Aspergillus niger*, bioleaching.

Introduction

Chromium is one of the most important component of stainless steel. India have large reserves of low grade chromite ore, containing impurities like silica which reduces the percentage of chromium in the ore and therefore make them inappropriate for industrial purposes. For the conversion of low grade ore into high grade quality by removing silica from the ore, bioleaching has been found to be more effective than various chemical processes applied for removing silica from ore. Bacteria and fungi are widely used for bioleaching studies^{1,3,4,6}. It has been reported that microorganisms like *Aspergillus niger* are capable of silica bioleaching¹⁴. Fungus releases metallic and silicate ions from minerals^{8,15}. Microbes utilize carbon sources and secretes organic acids¹¹. Production of organic acids depend on the growth and metabolic activities of the organism. Nutrients play an important role in this regard. Besides carbon and nitrogen, macro and micro elements play a vital role for proper growth and metabolic activities of *Aspergillus niger*. Therefore

sufficient growth and metabolism may enhance acid production which may increase silica bioleaching from chromite ore.

This study presents the effect of various macro and micro elements on a silica tolerant strain of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ for bioleaching of silica from Indian chromite.

Materials and methods :

Chromite ore : Chromite ore used in the study of bioleaching is obtained from the Sukinda Valley, Orissa, India. The ore was crushed to 200 mesh size and the silica content in the ore was estimated⁵.

Microorganism : The parent strain of *Aspergillus niger* was isolated from the soil of North Bengal and was cultured in Czapek Dox Agar media. It was then subcultured in the same media along with silica (90 mg/100 ml) to develop silica tolerant *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀⁵. These cultures were then used for the study of bioleaching.

Medium and culture conditions : Surface culture fer-

mentation was carried out using 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask, which contained 0.3 g chromite ore and 30 ml fermentation media consisting of glucose – 10%, NaNO_3 – 0.2%, KH_2PO_4 – 0.1%, KCl – 0.05%, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.05%. Each constituent of the media was made free of other metal impurities by chloroform extraction procedure. Chemicals for the medium obtained from Qualigens Excelar were of analytical grade. The required amount of aqueous solution of each was mixed well with 0.1 g of 8-hydroxyquinone and chloroform in a separating funnel, first at pH 5.2, then at pH 7.2. The chloroform dissolved impurities were extracted out. The process was repeated 2 to 3 times¹³. The solutions were made chloroform free by heating in water bath and sterilized separately. Sterile solutions of KH_2PO_4 , KCl , $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaH_2PO_4 , NaCl , CaCl_2 and trace elements ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NH_4VO_3) were prepared separately in triple distilled water and added individually to the sterile medium to attain the required concentrations, keeping all the factors constant, except one, effect of which was under investigation. Each experiment was carried out with one set of control which did not contain a particular factor in the fermentation media, which was under study. 6 ml inoculum containing 1.4×10^6 (spores/ml) spore suspension of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (spore suspension prepared in 10 ml sterile triple distilled water) was added to each fermentation media and incubated at 33 °C for 7 days. The initial pH of each fermentation media was 4.5.

Estimation of silica in the fermentation media : The organism leach out silica from ore into the fermentation media, which is then estimated colorimetrically by silicomolybdate method⁷.

Estimation of dry cell mass : The cells were separated from the fermentation media by filtration, washed with distilled water and filtered once again. The mass was dried in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h. It was then weighed to obtain the dry cell mass.

Statistical analysis : All data expressed as mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis were performed according to student's t distribution. The level of significance for two-tail test was determined from the table with critical values of t. The number of sample was 6.0 ($n = 6$).

Results and discussion

The result of the study revealed that the macro and micro elements are essential beside carbon (glucose) and

nitrogen sources (NaNO_3) for the mycelial growth, sporulation of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ and silica bioleaching. pH of the fermentation media after 7 days fermentation was found to decrease from 4.5 to 2.5–3.0, indicating that the organism may secrete organic acids responsible for bioleaching.

Effect of macro elements :

Fig. 1 shows that KH_2PO_4 (0.10%) has a stimulatory effect on both mycelial growth and significantly higher bioleaching of silica from chromite ore ($p < 0.001$) than control. This may be because phosphate is an integral component of cell and also forms high energy phosphate bonds which effect cellular metabolism and organic acid production.

Fig. 1. Effect of KH_2PO_4 on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM): (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (○) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 2. shows KCl (0.05%) has a significant stimulatory effect on both growth and bioleaching ($p < 0.001$) than control. K^+ maintain osmotic balance of a living cell and therefore may have some role in growth and development of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀.

Fig. 3. shows growth of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ and bioleaching is significantly increased in presence of 0.06% $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the fermentation media ($p < 0.001$). Mg^{2+} acts as a co-factor of ATP-dependent enzymes¹² and may activate the enzymes involved in acid production during silica bioleaching. Presence of divalent cation Mg^{2+} is essential for the release of silica, and its absence greatly inhibit the process². K^+ and Mg^{2+} are recognized as the two cations essential for almost all forms of life.

Fig. 2. Effect of KCl on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where n = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM) : (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 4. Effect of NaH₂PO₄ on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where n = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM) : (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 3. Effect of MgSO₄.7H₂O on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where n = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM) : (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 5. Effect of Zn²⁺ (ZnSO₄.7H₂O) on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where n = 6; values were expressed as mean ± SEM) : (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 4 indicates 0.05% NaH₂PO₄ increases the growth and bioleaching of silica ($p < 0.05$). Presence of NaCl and CaCl₂ in the fermentation media during bioleaching was found to have no significant effect on growth of *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ and silica bioleaching.

Effect of micro elements :

Figs. 5–9 shows that Fe²⁺ and Mn²⁺ have significant positive effect on mycelial growth and silica bioleaching

at 15 µg/ml Fe²⁺ ($p < 0.01$) and 10 µg/ml Mn²⁺ ($p < 0.01$) than control after using different concentration for the study. Fe²⁺ forms an integral part of fungal protoplasm and associated with many enzyme systems which may enhance silica bioleaching². Iron requirement is necessary for normal growth and sporulation of *Aspergillus niger* and iron deficiency reduces dry cell weight. Mn²⁺ also acts as a co-factor of many enzymes and its presence

Fig. 6. Effect of Fe^{2+} ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM): (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 8. Effect of Mn^{2+} ($\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM): (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 7. Effect of Cu^{2+} ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM): (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

Fig. 9. Effect of Ni^{2+} ($\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ (where $n = 6$; values were expressed as mean \pm SEM): (■) bioleaching of silica (%), (·) cell weight (mg/ml).

is essential for better release of silica². Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} have no significant effect at very low concentration in the fermentation media, but found to inhibit both growth and silica bioleaching at higher concentration. An increase in Ni^{2+} concentration (0.4 mM) resulted in a proportionate decrease in hyphal extension⁹. Co^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , V^{3+} when individually present in the fermentation media were

found to have no significant effect on growth and bioleaching processes.

From the present study, it has been found that silica bioleaching from chromite ore was increased from 60.40% to 73.76% after optimization of chemical nutrients in the fermentation media and the optimized media composition is as follows : glucose – 10%, NaNO_3 – 0.2%, KH_2PO_4 –

0.1%, KCl – 0.05%, MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.06%, NaH₂PO₄ – 0.05%, FeSO₄·7H₂O – 15 µg/ml, MnSO₄·H₂O – 10 µg/ml.

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